

CHILD
RESCUE

Collective Awareness Platform for Missing Children Investigation and Rescue

D5.2 – Project Website and Web 2.0 Channels

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ChildRescue Project Profile

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Partners

	National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), Decision Support Systems Laboratory, DSSLab <u>Co-ordinator</u>	Greece
	European Federation for Missing and Sexually Exploited Children AISBL - Missing Children Europe (MCE)	Belgium
	The Smile of the Child (SoC)	Greece
	Foundation for Missing and Sexually Exploited Children – (Child Focus)	Belgium
	Hellenic Red Cross (REDCROSS)	Greece
	Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences (FRA-UAS)	Germany
	SingularLogic ANONYMI ETAIREIA PLIROFORIAKON SYSTIMATON KAI EFARMOGON PLIROFORIKIS (SILO)	Greece
	Ubitech Limited (UBITECH)	Cyprus
	MADE Group (MADE)	Greece
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Executive Summary

The D5.2 report accompanies and documents the design, implementation and deployment of the ChildRescue project web page and the setup of the ChildRescue presence in various Web 2.0 Channels.

The ChildRescue website can be found at the following http (or https) address: www.childrescue.eu.

Designed on the basis of most recent practices and principles for web design, the ChildRescue website follows a modern, but minimalistic and user-friendly approach, presenting in detail the project's concept and objectives, the consortium and the demonstrators, the relevant material and a special section for news and events, as well as a section for the ChildRescue blog.

In accordance with the initial communication strategy as described in D5.1 "Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement, Initial Release", social media will be utilised as a core communication mechanism during the ChildRescue project implementation due to the social nature of the project. In order to raise awareness and effectively use the network effect of social media, a number of different social networks have been selected, each serving a different purpose for ChildRescue: a Facebook Page [ChildRescue.eu](https://www.facebook.com/ChildRescue.eu), a Twitter shared account [@ChildRescue_eu](https://twitter.com/ChildRescue_eu), a YouTube channel [ChildRescue](https://www.youtube.com/channel/ChildRescue), a SlideShare account [ChildRescue2020](https://www.slideshare.net/ChildRescue2020), a ResearchGate [ChildRescue Project](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/ChildRescue_Project), and a dedicated LinkedIn group [ChildRescue](https://www.linkedin.com/groups/ChildRescue) for ChildRescue-related discussions.

Following the ChildRescue Communication Strategy (as defined in D5.1), the ChildRescue website and social media will be constantly updated allowing for the presentation of project results, publications, new, events and general progress, expecting also participation from partners, related projects, and the broader community, until the completion of the project.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose

Deliverable 5.2 falls into the context of the WP5 entitled "Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication" and, in particular, of Task T5.2 "Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Activities". Its purpose is to report and document the ChildRescue website design and implementation, as well as the establishment of the ChildRescue presence in selected Web 2.0 channels and social media.

According to the DoA, one of the objectives of WP5 is to establish a leading visual presence in online media, including a project website for the presentation of results, as well as an effective presence in social media channels to further spread excellence and raise awareness.

The material presented in the website and the social media accounts will be regularly updated by the ChildRescue consortium in alignment with the ChildRescue Communication Strategy defined in the Deliverable D5.1 "Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement, Initial Release", and the updated releases that follow.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable has the following structure:

- Section 2 provides a quick overview and description of the ChildRescue project web pages.
- Section 3 presents the social media in which ChildRescue has established a presence and explains the purpose of each one in relation to the dissemination strategy.
- Section 4 concludes this document, explaining the assignments and next steps for content management in the website and the social media accounts.

2 ChildRescue Website

The domain name of the project's website is childrescue.eu. It contains the name of the project, with the .eu extension denoting its European origin. The selected wording fulfils the primary requirements of a successful domain name: It is short, descriptive and easy to remember.

The web site is built upon the latest version of the WordPress platform¹, which is a free, popular and open source content management system (CMS), with flexible blogging functionalities.

RSS feed is by default enabled in the following website address: <https://www.childrescue.eu/feed/> for facilitating automated access to the ChildRescue news and blog updates in a computer-readable format.

For measuring the website traffic and monitoring the visitors' behaviour, a connection with Google Analytics service² has been established and configured. The data insights coming from the ChildRescue website can be accessed either directly from the website's back-office or from the Google Analytics interface.

It is also worth mentioning, that all images used for design purposes were retrieved from Pixabay³, under the Creative Commons CC0 Licence.

2.1 Design

The design of the ChildRescue website follows the latest trends concerning web design, having also in mind the special characteristics of the project's objectives. More specifically, the ChildRescue website exhibits the following properties:

- **A modern, clean and light interface**, with contrasting colours for the text and background to make reading easier on the eye and with vibrant colours being only used for emphasis (e.g. links) and with caution. Special attention and thought was paid to make this website's content more accessible to visitors and compatible with current user agents.
- **Easy navigation** to content through a comprehensive structure, that is implemented both on the front page and the various menus.
- **A clean and modern Typography** was utilized throughout the website with large fonts that are easier to read.
- **A flat and simple visual design** that leaves a positive impression and does not annoy the visitors, especially the returning ones.
- **A Responsive design** making the website respond and adapt to the user's behaviour and environment based on his or her device (desktop, tablet or mobile) and screen size.

Overall, the ChildRescue website is built on modern web design principles, focusing on usability, accessibility and intuitive navigation. As requested by the ChildRescue Communication Strategy (D5.1), the colours selected are compatible with the logo and the look-and-feel match the requirements of the project's nature and purpose.

A sample of the website's front page is presented in Figure 2-1.

¹ <https://wordpress.org/>

² <https://analytics.google.com/>

³ <https://pixabay.com>

Figure 2-1: A sample of the ChildRescue website front page

2.2 Structure

The structure of the site can be derived by the top menu visible at the right top part of the website. It is a two-level navigation menu that aims to guide the visitor in a simple and intuitive manner. At the time of this deliverable, it contains the following items:

- Home
- About
 - Concept
 - Objectives
 - Consortium
 - Demonstrators
- Material
 - Public Results/Deliverables
 - Research papers
 - Media Kit
- News & Events
- Blog
- Contact

The **“Home”** menu-item returns the visitor to the Home page, in the same way the logo, if clicked, does.

The **“About”** menu-item has all available information about the project, regarding the main concept behind it, the main objectives, the members of the Consortium and a more analytic description of the demonstrators and their important role in the project.

The **“Material”** menu-item will hold all public results of the project in the form of documents, deliverables, research papers and dissemination material, such as a high-resolution logo, brochures, short bios of partners, and other useful files and documentation for the press.

The **“News & Events”** menu-item is a blog-like section that contains all posts about news concerning the project, as well as events scheduled for ChildRescue partners to attend to or have been attended. It is the main place for those visitors who would like to stay in touch with the actual progress of ChildRescue.

The **“Blog”** menu option, on the other hand, is a blog space that will host periodically articles and special content, suitable for social media circulation. Partners of the Consortium, stakeholders and opinion leaders are potential Editors of such content, aiming to provide to the website’s visitors useful insights and updates about the scientific, technological and societal aspects of ChildRescue.

Lastly, the **“Contact”** section provides all means of communication between the visitors and the ChildRescue management.

2.3 Content Overview

A ChildRescue website page, typically, consists of 3 basic design parts: the Header at the top, the Footer at the bottom, and the Content in-between.

The Header, as shown in Figure 2-2, is the container of the ChildRescue logo, the navigation menu and the discreet search functionality. It is the same for all pages. The header is marked as *fixed*, which means that stays always on top, even if you scroll down the page.

Figure 2-2: ChildRescue website Header

The Footer (Figure 2-3), includes 3 columns of information: the first is a short introduction to ChildRescue project, followed by a statement about EU financing, the second is a menu with the most useful material and news items, and the third is a “contact-us” area that exhibits the project’s e-mail address and the related social media links.

Figure 2-3: ChildRescue website Footer

The Content part can be divided into two different approaches: the front page and the inside pages.

2.3.1 Content – Front Page

The front-page approach consists of 5 horizontal sections, as depicted in Figure 2-4, that aim to attract the visitor’s interest and briefly inform him or her about the various aspects of the project. Therefore, we have:

- 1) The Slider section, where a few large images describe the incentives and inspiration behind the ChildRescue concept. In other words, we define the problem ChildRescue will attempt to solve.
- 2) The About section, where, in a few words, the ChildRescue purpose and scope is presented.
- 3) The Approach section, where the “How” is answered, by describing the methods and technologies that will be used in the project
- 4) The Call-to-Action section, which is a tool to direct the visitors to actually do something.
- 5) The News & Events section, where the most recent posts regarding the ChildRescue progress will appear in chronological order.

Figure 2-4: Front page content sections

250,000
Cases Of Missing Children Are Annually Reported In The EU.
Most Of Them Are Young People That Run Away From Home.

WHAT IS CHILDRSCUE ABOUT?
ChildRescue is an EU funded project that aspires to **effectively reduce** the primary period between the moment a child is reported missing and the one when it is found, and to help **predict and prevent** the disappearance of Children in Migration, by **increasing accuracy and timeliness** of publicly and privately available information, by performing **evidence-based predictions** on the whereabouts of children in distress, and by providing **location-based audience targeting** of mobile alerts. ChildRescue will be instrumental in leveraging **collective creativity, resourcefulness and action** for a meaningful cause: to expedite more rapid and effective **prevention and resolution** of missing children cases, reducing the risks for the children.

[Read more](#)

APPROACH
Technologies that will be employed by ChildRescue during the investigation of missing children

- Profiling**
Information from psychological reports and physical characteristics is augmented by the on-line presence and behaviour of the missing child, which is explored using Sentiment and Social Network Analysis techniques. This leads to the construction of a multifaceted personal profile able to reveal potentially hidden moods, activities, influences and acquaintances.
- Coordination**
Through an analytics interface, the response organizations, the search and rescue teams, and caretakers track progress of the investigation and gain insights on the current status and next steps. In addition, they share data in a privacy-aware environment and exchange ideas through a transparent, uninterrupted public information flow.
- Action**
In the core of ChildRescue lies the Collective Intelligence concept. Citizens and volunteers will be acting as "investigation social sensors" through real-time geofencing technologies that alert and update only those individuals located in the geographic area proximate to a point of interest (e.g. location that the missing child was last seen). A crowd-validation methodology will be introduced to evaluate the consistency of reported information.
- Archiving**
ChildRescue supports the responsible authorities and organizations to handle the case's closure in a secure and privacy-respectful manner. Semantic annotation of the documentation and lessons learnt of the case is provided internally in order to support its retrieval in case of similar cases in the future.

FOLLOW US ON SOCIAL MEDIA!
Stay up-to-date with the latest ChildRescue news, events and more!

[Show your Support](#)

NEWS & EVENTS
Keep in touch with ChildRescue progress

- March 13, 2018**
CHILD RESCUE
1st Plenary meeting announcement
ChildRescue first plenary meeting will take place in Limassol, Cyprus at the end of June 2018. It will be hosted [-]
[admin](#) [Read More](#)
- February 8, 2018**
CHILD RESCUE
ChildRescue at CAPSSI event in Brussels
On 14-15 February, Child Rescue partners attended the CAPSSI event Connected Technologies for Social Good event in Brussels. The workshop [-]
[admin](#) [Read More](#)
- January 02, 2018**
CHILD RESCUE
Kick-off meeting
The ChildRescue kick-off meeting took place in Athens on 18 and 19 of January 2018 hosted by NTUA.
[admin](#) [Read More](#)

2.3.2 Content – Inside Pages

The rest of the pages, also called inside pages, can be categorized into “static content” pages and “dynamic content” pages. A static content inside page usually contains information that is not supposed to alter frequently. Typical examples for the ChildRescue website are: the Consortium page, the project’s Concept page, or the Contact page. On the other hand, we have pages with content that changes frequently, such as the News or the Blog section. Images of both cases are presented in the Figures that follow.

Figure 2-5: Example of a static inside page

ChildRescue logo: Collective Awareness Platform for Missing Children Investigation and Rescue

Navigation: Home About Material News & Events Blog Contact

Consortium

The members of the consortium:

Logo	Organisation name	Short name	Country
	National Technical University of Athens, Decision Support Systems Laboratory, DSSLab (Co-ordinator)	NTUA	Greece
	European Federation for Missing and Sexually Exploited Children AISBL – Missing Children Europe	MCE	Belgium
	The Smile of the Child	SOC	Greece
	Foundation for Missing and Sexually Exploited Children – Child Focus	CF	Belgium
	Hellenic RED CROSS	REDCROSS	Greece
	Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences	FRA-UAS	Germany
	SingularLogic ANONYMI ETAIREIA PLIROFORIAKON SYSTIMATON KAI EFARMOGON PLIROFORIKIS	SILO	Greece
	Ubitech Limited	UBITECH	Cyprus
	MADE Group	MADE	Greece
	Suite5 Data Intelligence Solutions LTD	SUITE5	Cyprus

Recent Posts

- > 1st Plenary meeting announcement
- > ChildRescue at CAPSSI event in Brussels
- > Kick-off meeting

Archive

- > March 2018
- > February 2018
- > January 2018

Figure 2-6: Example of a dynamic inside page

CHILD RESCUE
Collective Awareness Platform for Missing Children Investigation and Rescue

Home About Material News & Events Blog Contact

Category: News-Events Home > News-Events

1st Plenary meeting announcement
 March 13, 2018
 ChildRescue first plenary meeting will take place in Limassol, Cyprus at the end of June 2018. It will be hosted [...]
 Edit

ChildRescue at CAPSSI event in Brussels
 February 16, 2018
 On 14-15 February, Child Rescue partners attended the CAPSSI event Connected Technologies for Social Good event in Brussels. The workshop [...]
 Edit

Kick-off meeting
 January 22, 2018
 The ChildRescue kick-off meeting took place in Athens on 18 and 19 of January 2018 hosted by NTUA.
 Edit

Recent Posts

- > 1st Plenary meeting announcement
- > ChildRescue at CAPSSI event in Brussels
- > Kick-off meeting

Archive

- > March 2018
- > February 2018
- > January 2018

2.3.3 Special Features

A very special and quite uncommon feature of the ChildRescue website is an open source plugin available at [NotFound.org](http://notfound.org/)⁴ that replaces the standard HTTP 404 error page with a page showing the poster of a missing child (see example in Figure 2-4) when a site's page is not found (e.g. when a link is broken). This is one of the most common error pages that a visitor may encounter during the exploration of a website and it is truly smart idea to use this page to raise awareness about the cause of the Organisations involved in the ChildRescue project.

⁴ <http://notfound.org/>

Figure 2-7: Example of an error page shown to a visitor instead of the standard 404 page

Whoops! This page either doesn't exist, or has gone missing. You can [click here to go back](#), or [click here](#) to go to the front page of ChildRescue. But before you do, take a look to see if you recognize the missing child below.

PAGE NOT FOUND, NEITHER IS SAMEEM FAZLI.

M I S S I N G	 SAMEEM FAZLI 14/07/2009	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 8 years old • ΚΑΤΩ ΠΑΤΗΣΙΑ (ΑΘΗΝΑ) • Την Τρίτη στις 14 Ιουλίου 2009 στις 20:30 εξαφανίστηκε από την περιοχή των Κάτω Πατησίων ο ανήλικος Fazli (επίθετο) Sameem (όνομα), ο οποίος κατάγεται από το Αφγανιστάν και διαμένει στην Αυστρία. Ο Sameem ήρθε πριν λίγες ημέρες στην Ελλάδα μαζί με τον πατέρα του για διακοπές. Ο Sameem είναι 8,5 ετών, έχει ύψος 1,40 cm, είναι αδύνατος, έχει σκουρόχρωμη επιδερμίδα, μαύρα μάτια και μαύρα κοντά μαλλιά. Την ημέρα που εξαφανίστηκε φορούσε μπλε μπλουζάκι, μπλε τζιν παντελόνι και μαύρα αθλητικά. ΛΟΓΩ ΤΩΝ ΣΥΝΘΗΚΩΝ ΕΞΑΦΑΝΙΣΗΣ ΥΠΑΡΧΟΥΝ ΣΟΒΑΡΕΣ ΕΝΔΕΙΞΕΙΣ ΟΤΙ ΤΟ ΠΑΙΔΙ ΒΡΙΣΚΕΤΑΙ ΣΕ ΑΜΕΣΟ ΚΙΝΔΥΝΟ. Ο SAMEEM ΑΝΤΙΜΕΤΩΠΙΖΕΙ ΠΡΟΒΛΗΜΑ ΥΓΕΙΑΣ ΚΑΙ ΔΕΝ ΜΙΛΑ ΚΑΘΟΛΟΥ ΕΛΛΗΝΙΚΑ. <p style="text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">MISSING CHILDREN? 116 000 THE EUROPEAN HOTLINE FOR MISSING CHILDREN</p>
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Missing Children Europe

I made better use of my 404-page by publishing this picture of a missing child with

not found.org

If you also use Wordpress, you can [help find missing children too](#).

3 Social media accounts

At the time being, ChildRescue has established its presence in 6 social networks as depicted in the table below, along with the respective web address. Each of them is presented in detail in the sections that follow.

Table 3-1: ChildRescue in Social Media

Social Network	ChildRescue Account	URL
	ChildRescue.eu	https://www.facebook.com/childrescue.eu/
	@ChildRescue_EU	https://twitter.com/ChildRescue_eu
	ChildRescue.eu	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCjhbXvHxGudlLpMYaXoQaQ
	ChildRescue	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/13581101
	ChildRescue2020	https://www.slideshare.net/childrescue2020
	ChildRescue	https://www.researchgate.net/project/ChildRescue

All partners and supporters of ChildRescue are encouraged to follow the above social media accounts and contribute content by using the hashtag **#ChildRescueEU** whenever possible, or by re-posting ChildRescue content.

3.1 Facebook Page

The main tool of communication with the public, nowadays, for any type of Organisation or Cause, is a Facebook public page. For this purpose, the [ChildRescue.eu](https://www.facebook.com/childrescue.eu) community page was created in English, so as to make contact with the ChildRescue audience and present mainstream information about the project, i.e. blog posts, related news and events.

Facebook, along with Twitter, will play a primary role in raising awareness and distribute related information, mainly due to the social aspect of the project.

Figure 3-1: An instance of the ChildRescue Facebook page

3.2 Twitter shared Account

ChildRescue's presence in Twitter goes by the account handle [@ChildRescue_EU](#) and the respective profile page is depicted in Figure 3-2. It is a shared account, meaning that multiple users can share the account without having to share the password, much like a facebook page. In order to manage the account and assign team members, one would need to use the TweetDeck teams feature, as shown in Figure 3-3.

This account will be frequently used in order to publish announcements and original ChildRescue content. In addition, several, relevant to the project, accounts and hashtags will be monitored systematically to identify content of interest and gain follow-backs, while the account will post content from other websites and re-tweet other accounts on important matters so as to attract more followers and maintain an active profile.

Figure 3-2: An instance of the ChildRescue Twitter profile

Figure 3-3: The ChildRescue shared account administration panel (tweetdeck)

3.3 YouTube Channel

A ChildRescue YouTube channel was created and configured for uploading and sharing any official ChildRescue videos, tagged appropriately in order to optimize search and access.

Target viewers will be allowed to subscribe, watch and comment the ChildRescue video content, as well as to show their approval and support.

Figure 3-4: An instance of the ChildRescue YouTube Channel

3.4 LinkedIn Group

A LinkedIn group is a discussion space for professionals of the same industry or with similar interests. With this in mind, the [ChildRescue](#) group was established as a place for collaboration and discussion among possible stakeholders and professionals regarding the cause and the methodology of ChildRescue, since it is a multi-faceted subject that touches many sciences and professions.

Figure 3-5: An Instance of the ChildRescue LinkedIn discussion group

3.5 SlideShare Account

SlideShare is a Web2.0 slide hosting service, owned by LinkedIn. Within the framework of the ChildRescue project, SlideShare will accommodate the project’s public presentations that are to be

created and provided for various events and occasions. Uploading and sharing (publicly or privately) these presentations will increase the diffusion of ChildRescue's public results in social networks.

Figure 3-6: ChildRescue Slideshare account

The screenshot displays the Slideshare profile for ChildRescue. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Slideshare logo, a search bar, and an 'Upload' button. Below this, there are links for 'Home', 'Explore', 'Presentation Courses', 'PowerPoint Courses', and 'by LinkedIn Learning'. A prominent banner for LinkedIn features the text 'GET HIRED FASTER' and a 'Register Today' button. The main profile section for ChildRescue includes a profile picture, an 'Edit profile' button, and statistics: 0 SlideShares, 0 Followers, and 0 Clipboards. The bio identifies ChildRescue as an NGO/Public Service with the website www.childrescue.eu. A detailed bio paragraph describes the organization's mission for 2020. To the right, a 'You have no uploads' message is displayed, along with a row of five suggested upload categories: 'How To Guides', 'Travel', 'Quotes', 'Inspirational', and 'Trends'.

3.6 ResearchGate Project

ResearchGate is an academic social networking site, where researchers and scientists can share papers, ask questions and seek collaboration. A research team is offered also the ability to create a "Project", a collaboration space for all research and work on a particular field.

In this context, a "ChildRescue Project" has been created to host all public research results and papers of the project in order to increase the exposure of that work to a scientific audience.

Figure 3-7: ChildRescue ResearchGate project

The screenshot displays the ResearchGate project page for 'ChildRescue'. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Home', 'Questions', and 'Jobs' links, a search bar, and user profile icons. The project title 'ChildRescue' is prominently displayed, followed by the names of the project members: Minas Pertselakis and Christos Ntanos. A goal statement is provided: 'More than 250,000 cases of missing children are annually reported in the EU. Through an innovative approach on the missing children investigation cycle, ChildRescue will be instrumental in leveraging the collective awareness, resourcefulness and action for a humanitarian cause: to expedite more rapid and effective resolution of missing children cases. The project will also take special care for supporting the identification missing unaccompanied refugee minors, which is an emerging issue nowadays.' To the right of the project description, there are statistics: 1 update (0 new), 0 recommendations (0 new), 1 follower (1 new), and 8 reads (2 new). Below the project description, there are tabs for 'Project log', 'References', and 'Questions', along with buttons for 'Add research', 'Add update', and a dropdown menu. The 'Project log' section is active, showing a post by Minas Pertselakis dated Jan 26, 2018, with the text 'Kick off Meeting took place in Athens (NTUA) on January 18 & 19, 2018.' and 11 reads. The post includes 'Comment' and 'Share' links.

4 Conclusions

This report intended to briefly present the ChildRescue project website and the respective social media accounts and document their status and purpose in the framework of the project's communication and dissemination activities.

Any information related to the project progress, results, news and events will be constantly updated and published in the ChildRescue website. Moreover, interesting topics for discussion will be hosted in the ChildRescue Blog so as to create an active vibrant community and maintain the interest of the returning visitors.

As a project with strong social aspects, ChildRescue social accounts will play a pivotal role in reaching targeted audiences, diffusing and promoting the appropriate information according to the communication strategy of the project.

It goes without saying that in order for this strategy to succeed, all ChildRescue project partners should be involved as much as possible and in various ways in the social media promotion of ChildRescue. Some recommendations are the following:

- Prepare original content for the Blog section of ChildRescue website, that can later be diffused in the various social media channels
- Follow/like the ChildRescue accounts in the various social networks.
- Like, Share, or Re-tweet the ChildRescue posts on a regular basis, in order to ensure further dissemination to their followers.
- Mention the ChildRescue respective accounts in any post related to ChildRescue (e.g. participation in an event, news of interest, related articles) or use the hashtag **#ChildRescueEU**, if you create your own project-related content.
- Any research activities (e.g. participation to a conference, publishing a journal paper) should be added to the ChildRescue project in ResearchGate.